

ASSOCIATION OF SERUM LACTATE LEVELS IN SEPTIC PATIENTS WITH OUTCOMES IN INTENSIVE CARE UNIT OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Dr Waqar Anwar^{*1}, Dr Shehzad Ahmed², Dr Aizaz Ullah Khan³, Dr Noor wahab⁴,
Dr Babar Ejaz⁵, Dr Muhammad Hussain Azad⁶

^{*1,2,3,4,6}PGR Medicine CMH Abbottabad

⁵Grd Med Spec CMH Chhor

¹waqar78687@yahoo.com, ²shahxada8@gmail.com, ³aizazk832agmail.com, ⁴noorwahab_12@yahoo.com,
⁵babar05ejaz@live.com, ⁶azadkhh@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Waqar Anwar

Abstract

Objective: To determine the association and impact of serum lactate on outcome and ICU-mortality in patients with Sepsis and Septic shock

Study Design: Prospective Cohort study

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Medicine and Intensive Care, Abbottabad, from 7 Feb 2025 to 7 June 2025.

Methodology: Patients of either gender with age 18-65 years admitted with sepsis or septic shock in medical HDU and ICU were included in study. SOFA score, APACHE II score and serum lactate levels were noted within first 24 hours of admission. Impact of serum lactate on disease severity and association with in-hospital mortality was analyzed with Odds ratio.

Results: Three hundred patients admitted with sepsis were included with mean age of 46.93 ± 13.35 years. Respiratory system was most common focus of infection in 110 (36.7%) patients, followed by gastrointestinal in 73 (24.3%). Higher lactate levels were significantly associated with increased mortality (p<0.0001). Patients with severely elevated lactate had 3.98 times higher odds of death (OR: 3.98, 95% CI: 2.52 – 6.29, p<0.0001) compared to those with normal lactate levels. Median ICU stay was 9.0 days (95% CI: 7.3–10.7) for the severely elevated lactate group, compared to 12.0 days for both the normal and elevated lactate groups. Multivariate logistic regression identified lactate level (OR=1.865, p=0.043) and APACHE-II score (OR=1.089, p=0.001) as independent predictors of mortality.

Conclusion: Hyperlactatemia is predictor of disease severity and linked with higher odds of in-hospital mortality in comparison to normal lactate levels.

INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is the host response to an infective stimulus leading to severe organ damage and septic shock which is a sequelae leads to marked metabolic derangements and circulatory compromise.⁽¹⁾ The mounting global burden of sepsis is a challenge for critical care physicians because of clinical, pathophysiological, molecular and

metabolic complexity.⁽²⁾ According to recent published data, there are around 49 million documented cases of sepsis and 11.9 million sepsis-related deaths, which is around 19.8% of all deaths globally.⁽³⁾ Sepsis and septic shock declared as a health priority by World Health Organization (WHO) due to overall incidence of 20-

35% worldwide sepsis-related deaths, which is higher with advancing age reaching up to 45% of overall mortality.⁽⁴⁾ The important confounding and contributing factors of high sepsis-related mortality are advanced age, comorbidities, increase in invasive procedures, use of immunosuppressive drugs, and unjust use of antibiotics leading to antibiotic resistance.⁽⁵⁾ Sepsis is related to marked metabolic abnormalities including elevated serum lactate levels and metabolic acidosis corresponding to cellular dysfunction in septic disease, hence, hyper-lactatemia is useful laboratory marker of sepsis severity.⁽⁶⁾

Lactate plays a vital role in cellular metabolism but it accumulates in blood in the presence of septic illness causing cellular dysfunction and metabolic acidosis leading to circulatory collapse.⁽⁷⁾ Lactate levels of more than 2 mmol/L are significantly linked with severe illness while levels more than 4-8 mmol/L are associated with severe organ dysfunction and mortality.⁽⁸⁾ Lactic acidosis usually occurs in conditions such as sepsis, hypoxia, shock, chronic liver disease, trauma and strenuous exercise, mitochondrial defects, drug intoxication and cancer related illness which poses a significant threat to organ dysfunction and high mortality in critical care setups.⁽⁹⁾

Despite studies, the association of lactate derangement in sepsis and its predictive association with sepsis severity and mortality remains unclear. There are limited local studies related to serum lactate effects on outcome in sepsis patients. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to ascertain the association of serum lactate in patients of sepsis and septic shock with disease severity and in-hospital mortality. It will guide critical care specialist to foresee the importance of high lactate levels in septic patients to optimize targeted antibiotic therapy and will also minimize mortality associated with hyperlactatemia.

METHODOLOGY

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Medicine and Critical Care at Combined Military Hospital, Abbottabad, from 7 Feb 2025 to 7 Jun 2025, over a period of 4 months. Ethical approval was obtained from the hospital's ethical review board prior to study commencement (ERBC # CMH-ATD-ETH-175-MED-24). The sample size of 285 was calculated using the Open Epi online sample size calculator, considering a confidence level of 95%, a

margin of error of 5%, a reported global incidence of 48.9 million cases of sepsis, with a 24.5% mortality rate.⁽¹⁰⁾ A consecutive non-probability sampling technique was employed.

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients of either gender, aged 18-65 years, admitted to the medical HDU or ICU with clinical and laboratory evidence of sepsis or septic shock were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients outside the specified age range, anemia, pregnancy, acute myocardial infarction (MI), and terminal illness, malignancy, on chemotherapy or receiving long-term corticosteroids or immunosuppressant were excluded.

Following ethical approval, all patients meeting the Sepsis-3 criteria (The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock) were enrolled. Sepsis was defined as organ dysfunction secondary to infection with a Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score of 2 or more. Septic shock was diagnosed in patients with sepsis who exhibited circulatory collapse requiring vasopressor support to maintain a mean arterial pressure (MAP) of ≥ 65 mmHg and had serum lactate levels > 2 mmol/L in the absence of hypovolemia.⁽¹¹⁾ Informed consent was obtained from patients or their attendants after explaining the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study. Patient anonymity was ensured at every stage. The study recorded demographic variables including age, gender, comorbid conditions, body mass index (BMI), and the source of sepsis. Serum lactate levels were measured within 24 hours of admission to assess disease severity and were classified as normal (< 2 mmol/L), hyperlactatemia (2.1 - 4.0 mmol/L) or severely elevated (> 4 mmol/L).⁽¹²⁾ The SOFA score was calculated within 24 hours of admission to ICU.⁽¹³⁾ The Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE-II) score was determined after 24 hours of admission in ICU. Patients were followed through out their hospital stay. The primary outcomes included the need for inotropic and ventilatory support, mortality within 72 hours of HDU/ICU admission, and 28-day mortality. Secondary outcomes included the length of hospital stay. Lactate levels were correlated with disease severity, complications, recovery, and in-hospital mortality.

Data was analyzed using SPSS v25.0. Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Continuous variables such as age, BMI, hospital stay, SOFA score, and APACHE-II score were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data or median (interquartile range) for skewed data. Categorical variables including gender, comorbidities, infection source, vasopressor support, ventilatory support, and mortality were presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between serum lactate level and outcomes were evaluated using the Chi-square or Fisher’s exact test. The independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test was applied for comparing SOFA / APACHE-II scores between survivors and non-survivors. A multivariate logistic regression model was used to identify independent predictors of mortality and ICU stay, adjusting for confounders such as age, gender and comorbidities. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Three hundred patients admitted with sepsis were included in study with mean age of 46.93 ± 13.35 years including 170 (56.7%) males and 130 (43.3%) females. Respiratory system was the most common focus of infection seen in 110 (36.7%) patients, followed by gastrointestinal (GIT) in 73 (24.3%), neurological in 44 (14.7%), genitourinary (GUT) in 32 (10.7%) and hematological in 31 (10.3%) patients. The patients had different comorbid conditions with diabetes mellitus being the most common one found in 54 (18%) patients. Rest of the comorbid conditions have been summarized in Table-I. Normal (<2.0 mmol/L) lactate levels were present in 204 (68%), Hyperlactatemia (Serum lactate 2.1 – 4.0 mmol/L) in 80 (26.7%) patients while 16 (5.3%) patients had severely elevated (>4.0 mmol/L) serum lactate. In terms of clinical outcomes, 73 (24.3%) patients were ventilated within 24 hours of admission while 114 (38%) of patients required vasopressors. Median SOFA and APACHE-II score of patients was 6.00 (4.00) and 8.00 (9.00) respectively with the median ICU stay of 7.00 (3.75) days (Table-I).

Table-I: Basic Parameters of studied participants (n=300)

Basic Parameters		n = 300
Age (mean years ± SD)		46.93 ± 13.35
Gender	Male	170 (56.7%)
	Female	130 (43.3%)
Comorbid Conditions	Diabetes	54 (18%)
	Hypertension	17 (5.7%)
	Ischemic Heart Disease	3 (1%)
	Chronic Kidney Disease	2 (0.7%)
	Combinations	35 (11.6%)
	Infection source	Respiratory
	Gastrointestinal	73 (24.3%)
	Genitourinary	32 (10.7%)
	Neurological	44 (14.7%)
	Hematological	31 (10.3%)
	Miscellaneous	10 (3.3%)
Serum Lactate (mmol/L)	Normolactatemia	204 (69%)
	Hyperlactatemia	80 (26.7%)
	Severely Elevated Lactate	16 (5.3%)
SOFA score (0-24)	2 - 9	236 (78.7%)
	11 - 24	64 (21.3%)
APACHE II score (0-71)	0 - 24	241 (80.3%)
	25 - 71	59 (19.7%)

ICU stay in days [Median (IQR)]		7.00 (3.75)
Vasopressor Requirement		114 (38%)
Ventilated		73 (24.3%)
Outcome	Recovered	220 (26.7%)
	Expired	80 (73.3%)

Hyperlactatemia and severely elevated levels of serum lactate were seen in 85 (74.5%) patients who required vasopressor support to maintain MAPs > 65mmHg, while 29 (25.4%) had normal lactate levels (p<0.0001). Higher lactate levels were significantly associated with increased mortality (p<0.0001). Patients with severely elevated lactate had 3.98 times higher odds of death (OR: 3.98, 95% CI: 2.52 - 6.29, p<0.0001) compared to those with normal lactate levels.

Correlation analysis showed a moderate positive but significant correlation between lactate levels and SOFA score (p=0.536, p<0.0001) as well as APACHE-II score (p=0.437, p= p<0.0001). Kaplan-Meier survival analysis

was conducted to assess the association between serum lactate levels and ICU stay duration. The survival curves demonstrated distinct differences among the three lactate groups: patients with severely elevated lactate had the shortest survival, while those with normal lactate levels exhibited the longest survival duration. Median ICU stay was 9.0 days (95% CI: 7.3-10.7) for the severely elevated lactate group, compared to 12.0 days for both the normal and elevated lactate groups. The log-rank test revealed a statistically significant difference in survival distributions across groups (log-rank p=0.021), indicating that higher lactate levels were associated with worse survival outcomes (Figure-1).

Figure-1. Kaplan-Meier survival curve showing cumulative survival over ICU stay for serum lactate levels

Multivariate logistic regression identified lactate level (OR=1.865, p=0.043) and APACHE-II score (OR=1.089, p=0.001) as independent predictors of mortality.

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates that serum lactate levels serve as a critical prognostic marker in patients with sepsis admitted to the ICU. A significant association was observed between hyperlactatemia and increased severity of illness, as reflected by higher SOFA and

APACHE-II scores. Renuka et al studied lactate levels, SOFA score and MEWS score and found SOFA score, a good but less sensitive predictor of mortality as compared to serum lactate levels which is an excellent and sensitive predictor of severity and mortality in ICU patients.⁽¹⁴⁾ In addition, patients with severely elevated lactate levels were more likely to require vasopressor support and mechanical ventilation, reinforcing the role of lactate in predicting circulatory failure. Weinberger et al found that lactate levels had predictive value in terms of circulatory failure and use of inotropic support, need of mechanical ventilation and also in terms of disease severity and mortality prediction.⁽¹⁵⁾

In our study, mortality rates were significantly higher in patients with hyperlactatemia, with those in the severely elevated lactate group exhibiting nearly four times higher odds of death compared to patients with normal lactate levels. These findings highlight the prognostic value of lactate in stratifying patients at high risk of adverse outcomes. Normolactatemia noted to have lower 28-day mortality than hyperlactatemia patients (17% versus 40%) irrespective of comparable physiologic parameters as explained by Sauer et al.⁽¹⁶⁾

The Kaplan-Meier survival analysis further corroborated these findings, demonstrating a clear association between higher lactate levels and reduced ICU survival (log-rank $p=0.021$). Park et al explained in Kaplan-Meier survival curves, higher 28-day mortality and significantly worse clinical outcome were noted in patients with higher SOFA score, Lac-SOFA score and Lac-scores ($p<0.05$).⁽¹⁷⁾ Pradhan et al observed that 47.17% patients admitted in ICU had high lactate levels ($>3.0\text{mmol/L}$) presented in septic shock with higher shock index (SI).⁽¹⁸⁾

Patients with severely elevated lactate ($>4\text{mmol/L}$) had the shortest median ICU stay and the worst survival outcomes. Song et al observed higher mortality rate at lactate levels of $>2.2\text{mmol/L}$ making 6-hour lactate level a prognostic predictor of severity and 28-day mortality (HR:3.61, 95% CI: 1.24-10.54, $p=0.0189$).⁽¹⁹⁾ Lee et concluded in his study that the optimal cut-off values of 6-hour lactate levels $>3.5\text{mmol/L}$ and 6-hour lactate clearance $<24.4\%$ were strongest factors for predicting in-hospital as well as 30-day mortality.⁽²⁰⁾ Similarly, Parthvi et al also observed that patients with sepsis admitted in ICU

having admission lactate levels of $>3.2\text{mmol/L}$ and lactate clearance of $<20\%$ had 100% mortality as compared to 59% mortality in patients who had lactate levels $<3.2\text{mmol/L}$ and clearance rate of $>20\%$.⁽²¹⁾

In this study, multivariate regression analysis confirmed that lactate levels (OR=1.865, $p=0.043$), along with APACHE-II scores (OR=1.089, $p=0.001$), independently predicted mortality. Similarly, in the multivariate regression analysis by Anderson et al, prehospital or admission lactate $>3.0\text{mmol/L}$ was a strong predictor of 30-day mortality with OR: 2.20, and $p=0.009$.⁽²²⁾ These results suggest that early lactate assessment can aid in risk stratification and guide clinical decision-making in sepsis management. Incorporating lactate levels into routine ICU monitoring may help in identifying patients who require aggressive interventions, ultimately improving sepsis-related outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In this study, it was concluded that there is a significant association between hyperlactatemia and increased severity of illness leading to higher in-hospital as well as 30-day mortality in sepsis and septic shock patients. Among various severity score studied, patients with severely elevated admission lactate levels ($>4\text{mmol/L}$) had the shortest median ICU stay and the worst survival outcomes with higher sensitivity in predicting patient outcomes.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The authors of this study are well aware of its limitations, the most important being the single center study and limited sample size. Sepsis etiological factors and pathogens were not studied in correlation to lactate levels and mortality. In addition, diagnostic accuracy of other severity score were not observed and compared with serum lactate levels in current study. Further studies like RCTs including different populations and larger sample size in multicenter approach are required for more accurate results. In addition, diagnostic accuracy of other severity scores including SOFA score, APACHE-II score, NEWS and MEWS score with risk factors should be studied before implication of results on larger scales on general population.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

WA: Concept and study design, Data Acquisition, Manuscript writing, Analysis & interpretation, Final approval

SA: Concept and study design, Analysis & interpretation, critical review & final approval.

AK: Concept and study design, Data Acquisition, Manuscript writing, Analysis, critical review & final approval

NW: Concept and study design, Data Acquisition, Manuscript writing, critical review & final approval

BE: Concept and study design, Data Acquisition, Manuscript writing, Analysis & interpretation, Final approval

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